

Mapping of stakeholders of veterinary medicine products' value chain to analyze their interactions and position regarding changes in AMU policy in Vietnam

Background

The misuse and overconsumption of antibiotics (AB) in livestock production in Vietnam resulted in antibiotic resistance that was addressed in the National Action Plan in Animal Husbandry and Aquaculture in 2017 implemented by Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. One of the strategies is to review, amend and implement regulations and policies on antimicrobial use (AMU). Since 2017, a number of laws and decrees have been deployed to progressively achieve a total ban on the use of AB in animal feed (see illustration 1).

Problem

There have already been strategies put in place, but they have been developed with rather legislative actors. It is not clear how these strategies are really understood, accepted and applied by the different stakeholders in the antibiotic chain and whether there is a risk that they are in contradiction with the socio-economic and political interests of involved stakeholders. Therefore, there is a need to identify the bottlenecks and barriers to the implementation of the current strategies and recommend possible solutions to overcoming these barriers, thus increasing the compliance of the legislation with the current situation in the sector.

Solution

Within the ROADMAP project, Stakeholders Mapping and Analysis (SMA) is being carried out including the literature review of the legislative framework regarding veterinary medicine products (antibiotic and alternative medicines) and development of a timeline for the implementation of veterinary medicine products legislation and in-depth interviews with key actors to explore their abilities to comply with the policy.

The aim of the SMA is:

- To map the veterinary medicine products value chain (see illustration 2) and characterization of the stakeholders in terms of power, interest and influence around the policy changes.
- To understand how the new regulations are acknowledged, accepted and applied by the different stakeholders in the AB value chain.
- To study the interactions between stakeholders and identify those who have an important role in the implementation of the strategy and determine the stakeholder's barriers and motivations for implementing these regulatory changes.
- To identify the levers to be activated for better communication and integration of the strategy.

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Keywords

Participatory approach, regulations, antimicrobial use, livestock production, Vietnam

Expected Outcome

- To provide recommendations to policy-makers to improve the acceptability of measures and develop new strategies to reduce AMU in livestock production.
- To develop local initiative to adapt to these changes (ex: written agreement between drug sellers and local authorities).
- To develop an AB-free or organic production to overcome these legislative barriers.

Expected Impact

- A change in behavior and perception of stakeholders in terms of AMU.
- A better implementation of and compliance with the veterinary medicine products legislation.
- A change in AMU practices by a reduction of AMU and an increase of the alternative medicines use.

Illustrations & Photos

Main legislation regarding AMU in Livestock Production in Vietnam since 2017

Illustration 1 - Main legislation on AMU in Livestock Production in Vietnam since 2017

Veterinary Medicine Products value chain and interactions between key stakeholders in Vietnam from focus group discussion, 2020

Illustration 2 - Veterinary medicines products value chain and interactions between key stakeholders in Vietnam from focus group discussion within the ROADMAP project, Hanoi, December 2020

Photo 1 - Construction of the veterinary medicine products value chain and interactions between stakeholders from focus group discussion with government members, feed company representative, veterinary medicines products producers and distributors, drug seller in Hanoi, 2020 (Photo credit: Nguyen Thi Thanh Hang)

Photo 2 - Drug seller in a drug agency, Bac Giang province, 2020 (Photo credit: Le Thi Thu Ha)

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